

LINGUISTIC CORPUS DESIGN AS NEGOTIATION: A CASE STUDY OF KAZAKHSTANI GANSU DUNGAN¹

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ABSTRACT

This study examines corpus design from the viewpoint of creating and using corpora for documenting and describing lesser-researched languages. Focusing primarily on Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan, a Sinitic contact variety spoken in Kazakhstan, we demonstrate that corpus design can be seen as a negotiation where the conflict between ideals and practical constraints influence the outcome. Corpus design is often teleological and represented as such retrospectively. At the same time, the process evolves under the pressures of external constraints, resulting in outcomes that do not necessarily fully align with the initial objectives. In this context, the paper discusses four methodological issues. For instance, while multilingual corpora have become more frequent, the current practices tend to presuppose clearly delineated languages where each corpus component can be labeled with an exclusive language code. This, however, fails to capture the 'fuzzy boundaries of languages' in actual communicative practices. Also, we argue that corpus design for lesser-researched languages, second language acquisition, and descriptive-documentative linguistics are intrinsically connected in a triangular relationship that is not considered sufficiently in earlier theory and practice.

KEYWORDS

Dungan, Sinitic languages, corpus design, field linguistics,
Central Asian minority languages

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INTRODUCTION

This section introduces the paper, outlines its research objectives, and defines key terms and concepts that will be explored in the subsequent sections. The introduction concludes with an outline of the paper's structure and the linguistic conventions we follow in transcribing and representing Dungan.

STUDY AIMS

This paper discusses corpus building as a tool for describing under-researched languages with often few available resources. Based on our ongoing research project on Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan, a Sinitic contact variety, and the authors' previous experience with language documentation and description, the paper argues that the creation of a linguistic corpus for such purposes is more accurately interpreted as a process of negotiation at the crossroads of the initial vision and adaptability into what comes up.

The discourse on corpora remains strongly teleological in a forward-looking sense: A linguistic need, such as documentation of a linguistic variety, is identified, and the created corpora, with its scope of materials, offer a solution to the issue. This, however, may be a mere 'backward projection'. As we will illustrate with Dungan, corpus design often evolves within the project's external constraints so that the end result crystallizes only *post factum*, frequently shaped even by serendipitous events.

Focusing on the concept of negotiation, this case study reveals four methodological issues, each of which are addressed in turn. To begin with, corpus design has focused on the representation and naturalness of the materials for a long time. In the case of lesser-researched languages, such demands may often have to be compromised to ascertain the project's feasibility. Also, the existing discourse and practice on corpus design runs the risk of downplaying the 'fuzzy boundaries of languages' (see Weber and Horner 2012) and extracting

idealized forms of languages. In terms of Dungan, many earlier descriptions of the language treat it largely as an 'ordinary' dialect of Mandarin (e.g., Lin 2012). Yet, our experience has shown that Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan has become a contact language intertwined with Russian, where separating borrowing, code-switching, and code-mixing remains a challenge and, in some cases, possibly an unfruitful task.

To address the issue, we propose the notion of a 'corpus of communicative activities.' Rather than trying to extract an essentialized ideal of a language, this approach, drawing from translanguaging theories, embraces the people's everyday discourse practices as the focal point. In other words, corpora can be constructed around communicative practices rather than around single differentiated and idealized languages. This approach is broadly applicable and particularly valuable in the multilingual context of Central Asia.

Furthermore, while *in situ* collection of language samples in corpus building is often voiced as the preferred approach, we argue that the distinction between *in situ* and *ex situ* collection is, in some instances, increasingly insignificant in our globalized world where mass migration is expected to increase further in the coming decades due to the global climate crisis.

Finally, as the last aim of this paper, we demonstrate that corpus design for fieldwork purposes, second language acquisition, and successful grammatical description are all intertwined and can be illustrated with a triangular model. This constitutes yet another difference in corpora for major languages and less-researched languages.

KEY TERMS

Dungan is a general term for Central Asian Sinitic Mandarin varieties spoken by Chinese-speaking Muslims in Central Asia. The varieties have approximately 110,000 speakers in total, and Ethnologue classifies Dungan as mid-sized and endangered (Eberhard et al. 2022). Two main varieties of Dungan exist: Gansu and Shaanxi Dungan. Less in number, there are also

speakers of several other Sinitic varieties in Central Asia included under the umbrella of Dungan by the local communities. This contrast between Gansu and Shaanxi Dungan traces back to the different geographical origins of the two Dungan groups. The linguistic and, to some extent, cultural differences between the two groups are noticeable, to the extent that speakers of different Dungan varieties often, but not always, use Russian as a lingua franca when communicating with one another. All examples discussed in this paper originate from Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan.

Dungan has a standardized written form based on the Gansu variety. Written Dungan differs from other written Sinitic varieties by using the Cyrillic alphabet, with no Chinese characters in use. Most Dungans lack even a passive familiarity of Chinese characters, and these characters are thus culturally alien in this Central Asian context. The present Cyrillic writing system was adopted at a series of conferences in Frunze (now Bishkek in Kyrgyzstan), 1953-1955 (Rimsky-Korsakoff 1967:357), which makes it novel in comparison to the long history of Chinese characters.

The term 'corpus' is used in various ways in linguistics. The mainstream approaches apply the term to a structured collection of machine-readable texts with varying amounts of accompanying annotation (see *inter alia* Laippala and Palander-Collin 2020:460). Meyer (2006:1-3) argues, however, that in terms of their medium, corpora can be divided into electronic and pre-electronic since some earlier creations, such as Biblical Concordances, were essentially corpora on paper. In practice, modern corpora are all in a digital format; consequently, this is the domain the present work focuses on. From the definitions above, it follows that a recording of a Dungan conversation by itself, without any further annotations, for example, remains primary data rather than a corpus.

Mosel (to appear) divides corpora into corpora of major languages and language documentation (LD) corpora.¹ This

¹ Since the study of lesser-researched languages remains less discussed regarding corpus design, some terminological variation

division is justified since the scope and creation process of the two, among other things, often differ. Also, Ostler (2008) demonstrates that the motives for creating and making available corpora of major languages and LD corpora are often distinct. Furthermore, while major language corpora have received substantial attention at the theoretical level, reflected in the publication of handbooks and articles, this is not yet the case for LD corpora, where theoretical investigation remains far more limited. Thus, justified reasons exist to distinguish LD corpora as a distinct format from corpora of major languages.¹ In the context of the authors' work on Dungan, 'corpus' refers to Mosel's category of LD corpora.

Field linguistics and language description are still, to some extent, unaware of their dependence on corpora. In other words, while many field linguists transform the results of their

exists. Chelliah (2021) uses the shorter form 'documentation corpora' while Vinogradov (2016) prefers 'under-resourced language corpora'. In this paper, while we follow Mosel's term 'language documentation (LD) corpora', we point out that the term 'corpora for under-researched languages' would be broader and more inclusive. First, if a difference is drawn between language documentation and description (Himmelmann 1998), not all corpora of under-researched languages are best characterized as documentation corpora. Second, 'under-researched' emphasizes no fundamental linguistic difference between 'major' languages with extensive research and 'minoritized' languages. Rather, the differences between the two are external: For instance, due to political and economic factors, many European languages have become 'major' global languages, unlike regionally spoken 'minoritized' languages whose speakers generally have no history of colonial expansion. As a result, such 'global languages' often have considerably longer and broader academic research histories, yet this has nothing to do with their intrinsic linguistic properties.

¹ Mosel's classification represents two extremes among a continuum, and corpora somewhere between the two are possible. Also, the term 'major languages' is problematic, given its vagueness. For instance, Kazakh ranks among the one hundred most spoken languages among the 7,000 currently used languages worldwide. While corpora of Written Kazakh have been created, no corpus of Spoken Kazakh existed before the initiation of the Multimedia Corpus of Modern Spoken Kazakh Language Project at Nazarbayev University (Filchenko et al. 2023).

fieldwork into searchable and machine-readable annotated texts on programs, such as ELAN and FLEx (FieldWorks Language Explorer), the similarity between these outputs and more prototypical corpora often goes unnoticed. In short, the rapid development of information technology in the past decades has resulted in a *modus operandi* where increasingly many researchers and research teams in descriptive linguistics and language documentation digitally process their source materials from the field into annotated outputs that resemble corpora in most of their essential aspects.

Sometimes, 'corpus' refers only to the aggregated materials deposited in an archive, such as the Endangered Languages Archive (ELAR) and DOBES (Dokumentation bedrohter Sprachen). Since the only major difference between before and after the moment of deposition in such cases is public (or at least broader access) to the corpus, the collected language materials become a corpus by being deposited and made publicly available.

In this paper, we nevertheless apply a broader view of corpora. When a researcher collects a set of recordings and annotates them, using this collection to draw inductive generalizations, even such non-published or pre-published annotated and machine-readable materials should be seen as corpora. Corpora of less-researched languages often remain unpublished. However, the current trend in research practices also points towards increasing online presence for such corpora, marking a positive trend toward more open research practices.

Even though some types of corpora have become the backbone of modern descriptive linguistics and language documentation, not all linguistic fieldwork and grammatical descriptions are based on corpora. For instance, an approach where the investigator explores the morphosyntax of the target language primarily through translating sentences from a *lingua franca* and then incorporating the examples into a descriptive text remains common. Even more clearly, a native speaker of an under-researched language may build his or her description

based on native intuition and constructed examples rather than collecting a database of source materials.

Finally, the study uses the notion of 'negotiation' to explain the complexities that arise in corpus design. Negotiation has been extensively studied in organizational behavior and management science (Brett and Thompson 2016). At the core, it involves resolving conflicting interests between different stakeholders. This study uses the term more broadly to refer to the process or processes for balancing a conflict that emerges between an ideal state and practical constraints. The broader meaning is necessary because the nature of conflict here is more abstract than in human organizations and their management, where the focus lies on human actors. In brief, for this paper, we define negotiation as the processes that, at least ideally, lead to harmonization and compromise between an ideal and practical constraints.

STRUCTURE AND LINGUISTIC CONVENTIONS

After the introduction, corpus design from the viewpoint of negotiation is discussed with a focus on four subtopics where ideals and realities collide. This is followed by a summary of the study's key arguments.

In the presented linguistic examples, we use Leipzig Glossing Rules ¹ and the included abbreviations when standardized abbreviations exist. Additional abbreviations have been coined when needed. Dungan examples are offered with five-line glosses. The first line offers etymological spellings with words of Sinitic origin written with Chinese characters. In contrast, those of Russian and Turkic origin are represented in Cyrillic. This is followed by the Cyrillic orthography of Dungan together with the standard three-line glossing format. While this approach to glossing may appear unnecessarily complex, it reflects the complex realities of language contact and

¹ <https://www.eva.mpg.de/lingua/resources/glossing-rules.php>, accessed 1 June 2025.

multilingualism that the Dungans have faced and continue to face daily.

The tones of Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan differ from those of Standard Mandarin. In this paper, they are marked as follows: ā '去声 realized as a high tone' (tone letters 1, 1), á '平声 realized as a rising tone' (tone letter 1), à '上声 realized as a falling tone' (tone letter 1), V 'neutral tone' (values adopted from Wang et al. 2015:40). The absence of a tone mark indicates our interpretation that the syllable is pronounced in a neutral tone, which typically applies to short grammatical morphemes that often undergo elision in their nucleus vowel. Importantly, tonal marking should not be interpreted in terms of Hanyu Pinyin, which is used for Standard Mandarin. For example, the noun 山 *shān* 'mountain' is pronounced in a high flat tone (tone letter 1) in Standard Mandarin, while in Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan, the corresponding word *caH* /sán/ 'mountain' is pronounced in a low-rising tone (tone letter 1). As the example illustrates, "á" in Dungan is thus used as a shorthand for the Dungan rising tone, the properties of which are somewhat distinct from the rising tone of Standard Mandarin.

CORPUS DESIGN AS NEGOTIATION

Drawing on a case study of Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan, the present section investigates corpus design as negotiation. The topic and the four ways of conflict between ideals and reality are mapped and discussed, the naturalness of the materials included in the corpus is addressed, the 'demarcation problem' in corpus design is dealt with, data collection location is presented, and the conclusion argues for a special interconnected relationship between second language acquisition, corpus design, and linguistic description.

THE AXIS OF NEGOTIATION

The present paper interprets corpus design as a negotiation process where idealized practices conflict with what is feasible or possible to accomplish. Earlier research on corpus linguistics has acknowledged corpora as an outcome of negotiation processes. For instance, Hunston (2006:156-157) states that corpora are compromises under practical constraints, the most important of which are "software limitations, copyright and ethical issues, and text availability." These inarguably constitute major challenges in corpus design. In investigating Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan, however, the present study argues that constraints rooted deeper in corpus design also exist. In brief, we focus on the axis of negotiation at the corpus design stage, which needs addressing early in an LD corpus project.

As summarized in Table 1, the present study demonstrates LD corpus design and must address four key issues. Challenges associated with each of these issues can be overcome with negotiation, as discussed further below. The first issue concerns the naturalness of the source materials and their representativeness. Here, the conflict lies between the ideal of creating a representative corpus with natural language versus difficulties in obtaining and analyzing such materials. The second conflict is about the demarcation of linguistic forms. In short, corpora often assume distinct languages where each element can be clearly labeled under one language. However, multilingual realities are often more complex, leading to what will be discussed later as "Schrödinger's words and morphemes."

Furthermore, the location of data collection presents another potential field of conflict where the ideal of *in situ* data collection stands in contrast with the fact that people are increasingly mobile in our global world. Finally, we highlight mastery of the target language as the fourth axis of negotiation, where the ideal of corpus creators speaking the target language fluently conflicts with the frequent reality of incomplete command. In this context, we propose a triangular relationship between second language acquisition, corpus design, and linguistic description, emphasizing the interconnectedness of these three elements.

Table 1. Components of negotiation in corpus building for fieldwork purposes

Component	Ideal	Challenge	Negotiation outcome
Naturalness and representation	Collection of natural language representing all major speech genres	Difficulty in obtaining and analyzing natural materials	Collecting materials feasible for analysis aiming for highest naturalness possible
Demarcation of languages	A single distinguishable linguistic form as the target	Difficulty in demarcating languages in a multi-lingual setting	Shifting the focus from clearly demarcated languages into multilingual practices
Location of data collection	Data collected <i>in situ</i> at the natural location of the speech community	Globalization and increasing mobility of people	Data collected where feasible, even including hybrid environments
Mastery of the language	People involved in design and annotating speak the language natively	Non-natives at work; acquisition of the language often neglected	Incorporation of SLA into corpus design and language analysis for their enhancement

REPRESENTATION AND NATURALNESS OF DATA

Especially since Biber's (1993) seminal article, representation has been broadly discussed in corpus design. Representativeness is often listed as one of the aims of corpora of major languages. In turn, certain authors have been skeptical about the possibility of creating a corpus of an under-researched language that is both representative and balanced. To illustrate, Vinogradov (2016) argues that this is impossible, resulting in the inability to use such corpora for any quantitative research.

Related to the above is the naturalness of the data contained in the corpus. Corpus design generally prefers natural data, such as spontaneous and unprompted conversations. The downside lies in that, unlike in the cases of more researched languages, natural data for under-researched languages is often challenging to obtain and/or annotate. This, in turn, leads to the question of whether the corpora of lesser-studied languages should be constructed with the same principles of representativeness and naturalness as the goals.

Full representativeness remains a distant dream for most of the work with LD corpora. However, this does not nullify the importance of aiming for each case's highest level of representativeness possible. Also, although there is a growing trend in linguistic fieldwork to focus on naturally-occurring speech instead of e.g., folktales only, full naturalness remains a goal that is hard to reach. Consequently, our underlying approach for investigating Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan has been the negotiation between representative and natural data versus data that is feasible to collect and analyze. This has resulted in incorporating non-conversational prompted materials into the corpus of collected speech. As an additional benefit, this demonstrates how the speakers of the target language perceive their language when spoken more consciously.

(1) 把我養下了回族家里。

Ба вә ёнхали хуэйзү жыни.

pá = və jòŋxā=li xwítsú tɛá=ne.

ACC=1SG give.birth=PFV Dungan home=LOC

'I was born in a Dungan family. (lit. I was given birth...)'

我们房子里十三个娃娃：十个儿子，三个丫头。

Ому фонзыни шы сангә вава: шыгә эрзы, сангә яту.

ò=m fòŋzə=ne ʂá-sán=kə vávà.

1=PL home=LOC ten-three=CLF child

ʂá=kə ázə, sán=kə játʰu.

ten=CLF boy three=CLF girl

'In our home (family), there are thirteen children: ten boys and three girls.' (personal fieldwork)

(2) 我给你 скину 把那个。你 можешь 吗 отпроситься? 我们 где-то 表四个上 начало.

Вә ги ни скину ба нәгә. Ни можешь ма отпроситься?

Вәму где-то бё сыгә хон начало.

və k=nì skʲinu pá =nē=kə. nì

1SG DAT=2SG send.PFV.1SG ACC=DEM=CLF 2SG

mozɛʂ=ma atprasʲitʲsʲa? ò=m g(d)ʲeta

can.PFV.2SG=Q get.leave.PFV.INF 1=PL about

pjò sɛ=k=xõŋ nateʰala.

o'clock four=CLF=DAT begin.PST.N.SG

'I will send you that (the information) now. Can you get leave from work? The beginning (of the show) is at about four o'clock.' (personal fieldwork)

Examples (1) and (2) above demonstrate that Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan speakers' conceptualization of their language differs from actual everyday linguistic performance. While the idealized form of the language avoids excessive non-Sinitic vocabulary (1), natural everyday speech (2) abounds in

elements of Russian origin. Also, the contrast shows that several phenomena encountered in the spoken language have not become phonologized, e.g., the contrast between the shortened vs. the long forms of several words, as in =kə vs. =k 'general classifier now mostly functioning as an individuation marker'.

Building the corpus of lesser-studied languages faces factors that affect the naturalness of the data, such as native speakers' attitudes and proficiency. Firstly, the prescriptive "puristic" language attitude in Kazakhstan influences Dungan speakers' use of language. As noted by our primary language consultant, who perceives herself as *шала* "shala," a Kazakh word literally meaning "half," and this attitude forced her to use "purer" Dungan instead of code-switching or drawing from lexical resources of Russian origin. Secondly, conscious of being recorded, speakers try to produce the most idealized sentences in "pure Dungan," which often conflicts with researchers' expectations of recording natural language. In other words, the observer's paradox¹ leads language consultants to speak "performed" and "self-conscious" speech (Schilling 1998).

Even though fieldworkers emphasize the use of natural language and attempt to record natural speech by different elicitation tasks, because of fieldworkers' presence, language consultants often try to speak slower, louder, or use Dungan phrases that they might not use on other occasions. Contributing to the image of the Dungan language in the scholarly discourse, speakers tend to control their speech thoroughly. To lessen the effect, we recorded phone conversations with the consent of both participants obtained for their use as research materials. This turned out to be more useful since the presence of another speaker made participants focus more on the content of the conversation rather than the use of language perceived as "pure." Another way has been to ask our language consultant to record

¹ Following the classical definition of Labov (1972:209): "...the aim of linguistic research in the community must be to find out how people talk when they are not being systematically observed; yet we can only obtain this data by systematic observation."

at home. Because of the presence of the recorder, it was less effective.

Different levels of language proficiency usually limit the genres of speech. The vocabulary of endangered language speakers may undergo attrition, and some speakers can only speak in specific genres, which is usually limited to everyday conversation or, even more drastically, tokenistic use of the language. At the same time, they might be unable to elaborate on the other topics without code-switching and code-mixing. Combined with the previously mentioned language ideology, these factors significantly reduce the chances of obtaining natural language data from many younger speakers of Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan.

In sum, unlike when creating corpora for the more researched languages in the world, for which abundant source materials of natural speech often exist, in LD corpus design, elements of non-spontaneous speech can also be incorporated into the corpus, as long as they are properly tagged for the user's benefit. The decision to include or exclude such materials can, therefore, be made by the end user of the corpus, depending on their specific research needs.

DEMARCATIION PROBLEMS AND CORPUS DESIGN

The times have now made multilingual corpora more acceptable. This positive development recognizes that the Western tendency for monolingualism is merely an illusion in our world, where multilingualism is the norm, not an exception. At the same time, multilingualism in the corpora creates a new issue, termed here the "demarcation problem." The crux of this issue concerns how to encode linguistic differences in a multilingual corpus. For instance, multiple languages can be coded into the corpora by indicating the language for each distinct element. To illustrate, in the context of multilingual Caucasia, where earlier corpus design practices have faced challenges, Gippert (2012:22) argues for fine-grained language codes that address the issue of marking multiple languages in a single corpus.

The aim to incorporate multilingual practices into corpora constitutes a great improvement in corpus architecture, defined by Zeldes (2020:49) as decisions concerning the conceptual division and interrelations of the kinds of objects a corpus contains and how these are represented. The current practices, nevertheless, mostly fail to address the issue of 'fuzzy boundaries of languages.' In other words, languages are conceptualized as mutually exclusive and clearly distinct units that can always be differentiated.

In practice, languages blend is due to language contact, and in some cases, it may result in difficulty delineating them clearly. As Romaine (1994:12) states, the idea of discrete and countable languages is possibly a European cultural artifact. Going a step further, Maoni and Pennycook (2007:1) state, "...languages were, in the most literal sense, invented, particularly as part of the Christian/colonial and nationalistic projects in different parts of the globe."

There is much truth to these claims connecting the idea of separate, quantifiable, and distinct languages with Western thinking. At the same time, language is a fundamental concept in linguistics. While recognizing the demarcation problem, we certainly do not advocate the abolition of the term 'language', but rather highlight how the quantifying approach poses challenges in corpus design.

Investigating Dungan and collecting the materials for the corpus collided with the demarcation problem. The Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan is now fully intertwined with Russian, and most speakers of the language are either bilingual or multilingual, as some Kazakhstani Dungans are also fluent in Kazakh or another regional language.¹ In some instances, drawing lines between Dungan and non-Dungan materials results in identification challenges, both of a practical and methodological nature. This can be exemplified by the Dungan word *машинэ* /maʃne/ 'car' (3). No other word for 'car' exists in the language. The word is widely known and used by the speakers of the language. At the same

¹ This also affects the language's morphosyntax. See Honkasalo (2024) for a detailed analysis of 'Russification' in Dungan.

time, Dungan speakers do not accept it as Dungan but rather consider it Russian, matching with its known etymological source in the language, namely *машина* /maʃina/ 'car'.

(3) 我连单另 *машине* 去呢。

Вэ лян данлин *машине* чини.

və lja=tálĩŋ maʃne tɕʰi=ni.

1SG COM=other car go=PROSP

'I will go by another car.' (personal fieldwork)

Unlike *машина* /maʃina/, however, many, if not most, modern loanwords-like components in Dungan discourse do not undergo phonological adaptation, so this fails to provide any clues for demarcation either. The key question consequently asks whether such elements in the source materials should be coded as Dungan or Russian (or, in the case of another source language, under that language). Such "Schrödinger's words" that manifest the features of both codes simultaneously are aplenty and typically belong to the semantic fields of objects and notions of the modern era, e.g., *самолет* /samolet/ 'airplane', *садик* /sadi:k/ 'kindergarten', and *цирк* /tsirk/ 'circus'.

Theoretically, the issues can be solved from three perspectives. To begin with, the coding in a corpus may focus on etymology, namely the diachronic aspects of language, and thus code elements of Sinitic, Russian, and Perso-Arabic sources with different codes. Alternatively, an approach focusing on native speakers' intuition would consider those words Dungan that native speakers acknowledge as such. Finally, the synchronic contact-linguistic approach would pursue the topic by considering how deeply the words are adapted to Dungan. Like in the case of *машина* /maʃina/, the three approaches may give conflicting results.

Furthermore, Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan manifests at least a few 'hybrid words,' the components of which come from different languages. The word for 'neighbor,' *хуэшьлин* /xuəʃlin/, appears as the most potential example. The first part likely has a Turkic etymology, cf. the Kazakhstani Ghulja Uyghur *хошна* 'neighbor'. On the other hand, the second part seems to derive from the Sinitic word *lín* (as in Standard Mandarin) 邻

'neighbor,' generally used in compounds. While word-internal components can be coded to different sources, the meaningfulness of this remains questionable.

Taking a comparative perspective, similarities abound in other languages spoken in multilingual settings, indicating that the challenges faced in the case of Dungan are by no means unique to this language. The demarcation problem has not been properly addressed in earlier corpus studies likely results from the fact that many widely-known corpora created in the past are based on European languages in societies where awareness of multilingualism has historically been less pronounced.

The situation of the Western Tibetosphere resembles that of Central Asia. Instead of a 'triangle of multilingualism' between Russian, the national language, and minority languages, multilingualism in the Eastern Tibetosphere is characterized by a complex relationship between Chinese (the national language), Tibetan languages, and (other) minority languages (see e.g., Roche 2018).

Geshiza, a Gyalrongic language of Sichuan in China, has been in intensive contact with Chinese over recent decades. This has resulted in a significant influx of Chinese loanwords into the language (see Honkasalo 2019), contrasting heavily with earlier Tibetan lexical influence. Like the case of Dungan, on many occasions, it remains challenging to establish whether a lexical element constitutes code-switching or borrowing. To illustrate, in (4) /tʂʰetsə/ 'car' has been borrowed from the Chinese *chēzi* 车子 'car'. The Geshiza, who are bilingual in Chinese, consider this word Chinese. At the same time, it has established itself, gaining wide use since no native word exists to denote 'car'. Again, phonology offers no extra help since similar recent lexical elements of Sinitic origin do not undergo phonological adaptation.

- (4) Geshiza (Honkasalo 2019:710, modified and translation corrected)
- | | | | | |
|--------------|-------------|--------------|----------------|-----------------|
| <i>sʰævi</i> | <i>tɕʰu</i> | <i>mdzə</i> | <i>ʋɛe-ræ,</i> | <i>tʂʰetsə.</i> |
| next.year | CONJ | exchange.INF | AUX.need-SENS | car |
- 'It needs to be changed the next year, the car.'

A corpus built on the principle of separate and discreet languages cannot handle the ambiguity of a word being simultaneously Sinitic and Russian any more than we can imagine Schrödinger's cat being simultaneously dead and alive. Shifting the focus offers a partial exit from the conundrum above. Most language documentation corpora are constructed language-centrally. As demonstrated above, this approach results in the need to essentialize and demarcate languages. On the other hand, we propose the notion of corpora of communicative practices where the focal points shift from languages to the communicative practices of speech communities. This proposal builds on the notion of translanguaging. Instead of possessing autonomous language systems, translanguaging posits that multilingual speakers use features from their unitary linguistic repertoire to communicate (Vogel and García 2017). In practice, many speakers of minoritized languages are now multilingual. When communicating, they draw from all their available linguistic resources.

Central Asia is a multilingual linguistic space where many speak several languages daily. Applying the notion of the corpus of communicative practices is particularly beneficial for capturing the linguistic behavior in such a space. In practical terms, this means documenting the daily practices of speakers of a language, such as Dungan, without regard to language and building the corpus around performance. Compared to the existing practices that emphasize distinct languages,¹ this approach would enable us to see a broader range of linguistic practices in the speaker community.

LOCATION OF DATA COLLECTION

Another aspect of LD corpus design addresses location, namely, where the source materials are collected. In terms of fieldwork,

¹ This claim is easily proven by inspecting the names of major available corpora that almost invariably include a single language name.

data collection branches into *in situ* and *ex situ*. In the former, the researcher collects data from a language community from their core location. This would prototypically refer to a homeland or location inhabited by the community for hundreds, if not thousands, of years. On the other hand, the latter refers to a non-conventional location, such as an immigrant community or a refugee camp.

The location of source material collection has been discussed previously. Many scholars, such as Williams and Comfort (2007:267), recognize it as acceptable when other, better options are challenging. At the same time, skeptical views surface frequently, voiced among others by Aikhenvald (2007:5):

Working with immigrant communities – if a language is well spoken in a home country – is also hardly advisable: many grammatical features are extremely prone to contact induced change and are likely to shift under the impact of introducing new – and losing old – cultural practices. But it is bound to give a skewed picture of the language's structure.

The bifurcation in location expresses an outdated understanding, disregarding human mobility that has sped up global migration flows, further likely accelerated by the global climate crisis that will potentially render some parts of our planet inhabitable. It also does not consider hybrid sources that may be created when speakers of a minoritized language interact in cyberspace. Furthermore, at its deeper level, the criticism of *ex situ* fieldwork may presuppose linguistic purism that perceives 'contaminated' contact varieties as inferior vis-à-vis to their 'purer' counterparts.

The Dungans themselves are an exile community originating from Western and Northwestern China under the rule of the Qing Empire (1644-1912). The Qing Dynasty's defeat in the first Opium War (1839-1842) resulted in various revolts across the empire, weakening its power (Khalid 2021:79). In other words, the perceived weakness and humiliating defeat made the ruling dynasty appear as less fit to rule, questioning its "mandate of heaven" (天命), namely the legitimate right to rule. As one of the rebel groups reacting to the changing geopolitical setting, the Dungans rose against the Qing Empire in a revolt

(1862-1877). As a result of its failure, they had to relocate to safer territory outside the Qing Empire. The Russian domains of Central Asia offered the most accessible alternative, resulting in the Dungan habitation of Central Asia attested today. Consequently, the presence of Dungans in Central Asia, at least in part, results from global politics with events taking place in faraway coastal China and offers yet another illustration of a political long-distance effect from an era before globalization.

A sizable part of our Dungan data originates from the Astana Gansu Dungan community. Yet, the original intention of the research project was to build the corpus from Southern Kazakhstan along the Kyrgyzstani border known as the heartland of Kazakhstani Dungan habitation. When the project's principal investigator was living in Astana, through mere serendipity, we discovered that a sizable community of Dungans now live in the city. This sizable community has never been documented in earlier research and exceeds several hundred families in the capital, often with many children. At the same time, it should also be noted that most Dungan families spend most of their lifetime in Southern Kazakhstan and moved to Astana within the last two decades. While approximately half of our corpus materials originate from the South, we have decided to incorporate materials from Astana into it. The mere practical dimensions dictate that not utilizing this opportunity would have been unreasonable.

Astana is the youngest capital in the world, having witnessed rapid economic growth and population expansion since Kazakhstan's independence in 1991. Before 1997, only a few Dungan families lived in Astana (at the time, Tselinograd), possibly even two. Therefore, it is hardly possible to talk of Astana as the historical homeland of the Dungan people. Nevertheless, a sizable community of Dungans has now settled permanently in Astana. Furthermore, as illustrated above, Central Asian Dungans have historically been migratory, with a history in the region of only approximately 150 years. Against this backdrop, it is reasonable to ask how long a linguistic

community must have resided in a location so that the data collection process is considered *in situ*?¹

Dunganological research has been greatly affected by linguistic purism. Descriptive grammars and earlier collected materials of the language exist. Examining Lin (2012) and Wang et al. (2015) as two representative monographs on Dungan grammar (in Chinese), it is clear that earlier research tends to treat Dungan as a rather typical Chinese dialect, although with some borrowings from Russian, Turkic, and Perso-Arabic sources. This contrasts with our findings that show Dungan in thorough linguistic contact with Russian and, to a lesser extent, with Turkic languages (see also footnote 5). Rather than trying to find the most isolated Dungan community with minimal historical relocation to discover the 'purest' shape of the language, the project has focused on this contact. As discussed above, a sizable part of the source materials originates from Astana, which had no earlier historical Dungan habitation.

In relation to this, an important factor to consider while building a corpus of a small group is the participants' age. Endangered languages have a low level of intergenerational transmission. Therefore, younger participants obtain a smaller vocabulary and tend to code-switch more often than older generations. Personal fieldwork done on Gansu Dungan speakers in Kazakhstan has shown that age is more important than location since younger participants from Southern Kazakhstan have demonstrated lower language proficiency than the older participants from Astana.

¹ While the discussion above focuses on the Dungans in Kazakhstan, similar issues are identifiable across the globe. To illustrate, thousands of Tibetans migrated to India after Tibet's annexation into the People's Republic of China. While becoming refugees was originally intended as a temporary solution, reconciliation between China and refugee Tibetans seems increasingly unlikely. As a result, many Tibetans have come to accept residency in India as a fact, not a temporary state. It is thus relevant to consider whether Dharamshala is a suitable place for investigating Tibetic (and other) languages. Following the arguments offered in this study, Dharamshala can now be seen as a part of the Tibetan-speaking world and a potential location for collecting corpus materials and conducting fieldwork with all the caveats that must be considered in *ex situ* fieldwork.

CORPUS DESIGN, SLA, AND GRAMMATICAL DESCRIPTION

Grammatical description and linguistic fieldwork are rarely discussed theoretically from the viewpoint of second language acquisition, save some notable exceptions, such as the role of monolingual fieldwork (see e.g., Everett 2001). In this section, we argue that a strong connection exists between the two.¹ Moreover, both are interconnected with corpus design, forming a triangular model of corpus-based language description in Figure 1 below.

While corpora of more researched languages, such as English, may be used for second language acquisition and the design of learning materials, the process of corpus design itself is usually not connected to the designers' own English learning process. In other words, a team member who creates a corpus of English or French is expected to know the language, often natively, and the process of corpus building is fully separate from SLA. In what follows, we nevertheless argue that LD corpora differ fundamentally in this regard. Specifically, SLA plays a key role in the negotiation process involved in forming LD corpora and should therefore be considered more.

Figure 1. The triangular relationship of corpus design, SLA, and grammatical description

Linguistic communities generally appreciate the researcher's efforts to learn the target language and attempts to

¹ This obviously does not hold in cases where the researcher is a native speaker of the investigated language, such as Tunzhi's (2019) grammar of Northwestern Stau (Sino-Tibetan, Gyalrongic).

use it in daily communication besides the research activities. Moreover, as Mosel (to appear) argues, the quality of the collected corpus data depends on the interaction with the local partners. Consequently, increased focus on second language acquisition, far from being time wasted, is likely to bring major benefits to any long-lasting description or documentation project of an under-researched language.

Russian departments worldwide rarely start their introductory courses by systematically reading *War and Peace*. Rather, due to a significant body of knowledge regarding SLA, the classes and courses typically proceed progressively from materials deemed easy to more demanding ones. The expectations differ when collecting source materials through fieldwork and analyzing their linguistic content. The current academic environment exerts considerable pressure on performance: Results are needed, and they are needed fast. By focusing on collecting materials that are ideal for corpus design, researchers may neglect the aspect of their own language acquisition. This results in working at a level of the target language that surpasses one's capacities, which is directly connected to negotiating the naturalness of the data discussed in the section on representation and naturalness of data.

Schneider (2011) argues that language learning is linguistic analysis. Given the close relationship between the two, it follows that the successful learning of the target language often plays a pivotal role in the success of a morphosyntactic description or language documentation project. For one, it enables the researcher to process and annotate more natural source materials, thus increasing the amount of available materials in the corpus and potentially increasing its representativeness, connecting the first and last points of negotiation discussed in this article with each other.

The connections go even further. Paying attention to SLA offers potential benefits to handling problematic situations in corpus design, such as when boundaries between languages are difficult to determine, as discussed in the context of the demarcation problem, the second axis of negotiation. While higher linguistic awareness of the language(s) included in a corpus will not solve all demarcation problems, it may contribute to settling some cases.

In sum, corpus design, grammatical description, and second language acquisition are all interconnected with strong synergy between the three. It is worth noting that benefits can flow in any direction in the triangular relationship. For instance, LD corpora can create learning and literacy materials for lesser-studied languages (see also Schneider 2011 on literacy development).

CONCLUSION

Drawing on the authors' work on Kazakhstani Gansu Dungan, the present paper argues that corpus design for less-researched languages is often a process of negotiation, which has not been sufficiently discussed in previous literature where fieldwork guides, for instance, often offer idealistic suggestions for corpus design. We identified four key axes of negotiation: naturalness of data, demarcation of languages, location of data collection, and linguistic knowledge of the target language by the investigators. The study demonstrated that corpora of less-researched languages may need to compromise more in some of the above, such as the naturalness of the data. At the same time, the issue of connecting corpus design with the acquisition of the target language is unique to such corpora when compared with the creation process of corpora for 'major' languages. Finally, shifting focus from the notion of distinct and independent languages into linguistic practices offers a potentially valuable new approach to studying multilingual spaces, such as Central Asia, since the demarcation of languages is not always straightforward.

ABBREVIATIONS

1 'first person', 2 'second person', 3 'third person', ACC 'accusative', AUX 'auxiliary', CLF 'classifier', COM 'comitative', CONJ 'conjunction', COP 'copula', DAT 'dative', DEM 'demonstrative', INF 'infinitive', LOC 'locative', N 'neuter gender', NMLZ 'nominalizer', PFV 'perfective', PL 'plural', POT 'potential', PROSP 'prospective', PST 'past', Q 'question', S 'single participant of an intransitive clause', SENS 'sensory evidential', SG 'singular'.

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